

Introducing Proficiency Badges for 'CLEWs' Nexus Modelling

We are pleased to announce the launch of the Energy and Resource System Modeling Proficiency Badge Scheme, a collaborative initiative born from the partnership between RE-INTEGRATE and Climate Compatible Growth (CCG). This innovative certification system aims to standardise and recognise modelling proficiency for the CLEWs Modelling tool.

RE-INTEGRATE, an EU Horizon Europe programme, is dedicated to re-thinking approaches for transdisciplinary integrated assessment of climate-compatible energy strategies from the African Union to the European Union; joins with CCG, a UK aid-funded research programme helping countries in the Global South pursue low carbon development. Together, we present this badge scheme as a transparent and community-driven endeavour.

It is crucial to emphasise that while this initiative emerges from our partnership, its true strength and longevity lie in the hands of the wider energy modelling community. We envision this proficiency badge scheme as a living, evolving system owned and driven by practitioners, researchers, and institutions across the globe. Our role is to initiate and facilitate, but the scheme's success and relevance will depend on the active participation and input from the entire energy modelling ecosystem.

We invite all stakeholders - from individual modellers to academic institutions, research organisations, and industry partners - to engage with this scheme, provide feedback, and help shape its future. By fostering a collaborative approach, we aim to create a certification system that reflects the needs and aspirations of the global energy modelling community.

This badge scheme represents a step towards creating a more interconnected, skilled, and recognized community of energy system modellers. It offers a clear pathway for skill development, encourages continued learning, and provides a standardised means of acknowledging expertise across different tools and contexts.

Objective: To establish a standardised certification system that benchmarks modelling proficiency in CLEWs modelling through a tiered badge system: Bronze, Silver & Gold that signifies modelling competency. An additional two-levelled 'Instructors' badge is also included to denote capacity building and instructing competence. Initially, this system will be deployed in a CCG/RE-INTEGRATE context, using the Open University (OU) 'Open Learn' platform, with a longer term aim of the badge system to become relevant for practitioners beyond these organisations.

Benefits of a Digital Badge System:

- Standardised recognition of modelling proficiency across institutions and tools
- Clear pathway for skill development and career progression in energy and resource modelling
- Encouragement of continued learning and contribution to the field; a convenient and effective means of recognising and rewarding accomplishments.
- Aid towards the creation of a community of practice around energy and resource system modelling (alongside CCGs's Energy Modelling Community (EMC) initiative)
- Flexibility to incorporate various modelling tools and approaches within the same framework
- Can increase awareness for: RE-INTEGRATE activities, CCG's Energy Modelling Platform (EMP) events and other similar capacity building programs.

Strategy for Development:

1. Design clear and transparent metrics for a modelling badge system
2. Align Badges with CCG tools and processes- namely CCGs's Energy Modelling Community (EMC) initiative and Energy Modelling Platform (EMP) summer school events
3. Utilise the Open University (OU) 'Open Learn' platform to enable: digital badge application, assessment, and issuance via LinkedIn's digital badge system ([LinkedIn Badge system](#)). E.g. Badge holders will have the icon in their LinkedIn profile with a description of what the badge represents
4. Create a peer review/ peer endorsement system to assess badge applications.
5. Award inaugural badges to relevant RE-INTEGRATE / CCG participants
6. Pilot test system (scheduled for Jan-August 2025)
7. Adjust badge system accordingly based on pilot testing (August - December 2025)
8. Establish partnerships with universities, research institutions, relevant industries, to recognize and integrate the badge system i.e. institutions within the OptIMUS Community and relevant international organisations (e.g. GIZ, IAEA, IRENA, UNDEP, UNDESA, IEA, UNECA); and the OpenMod community ([openmod-initiative](#)).
9. Expand badges to accommodate additional modelling tools
10. Organise annual conferences or workshops where Gold badge candidates can present their work
11. Develop a mentorship programme connecting Gold/Silver badge holders with Bronze & Silver-level learners (Links to CCG's EMC)

Peer Review and Validation Process:

The badge system operates through a rigorous peer review process that ensures quality and maintains high standards across the community. Gold badge holders play a pivotal role in validating Silver badge applications, while Silver badge holders assess Bronze level submissions. This cascading validation approach creates a self-sustaining ecosystem of expertise and knowledge transfer within the modelling community.

By leveraging the expertise of established practitioners, this peer review system ensures that:

- Assessment criteria are consistently applied across all applications
- Evaluation is conducted by those with hands-on experience in the field
- The community actively participates in maintaining the quality and credibility of the certification
- Knowledge and best practices are naturally shared between different levels of expertise

This structure also provides a clear progression pathway, where badge holders at each level contribute to the development of future experts, fostering a collaborative and supportive learning environment.

The process is overseen by the energy and resource modelling 'community', which will initially comprise of 'inaugural badge holders' who are necessary to begin the peer review process. As future members become accredited they will also be able to validate future badge applications. Key individuals from RE-INTEGRATE, CCG and Open Learn will have initial administrative roles within the process to ensure alignment with the scheme's objectives and standards.

- Inaugural Badge Holders: For personal and selection process, see list at the end of document
- RE-INTEGRATE: Leigh Martindale l.martindale@imperial.ac.uk
- CCG: Rudolph Yeganyan r.yeganyan1@lboro.ac.uk
- Open Learn 'Course Manager': Ashutosh Bhagurkar - ashutosh.bhagurkar@open.ac.uk

Implementation:

- Participants apply for a badge via the Open University's 'Open Learn' platform.
- They must upload the required documentation for that particular badge.
- During the selected assessment windows (or by participant request), the open learn grading platform is checked by established badgeholders (initially these are the inaugural badgeholders) who have access to the openlearn platform as 'teachers'.
- Specifically, the CCG tool lead will be responsible for ensuring the grading platform is managed appropriately - for CLEWs this is currently Kane Alexander (k.alexander@imperial.ac.uk) as of November 2025.

- Once directed to the Open Learn Platform, badgeholders will assess the applicant's submitted/uploaded evidence (e.g., project reports, publications) against the badge criteria and decide to pass or fail.
- If passed, participants follow emailed instructions to receive a digital badge for LinkedIn profile and (if badge level above bronze) the process to become a registered 'teacher' to validate future badge applicants.

Badge Levels:

The Intended Learning Objectives (ILO) will be similar across the board in terms of expectations i.e. similar requirements for knowledge & understanding, cognitive skills, and practical skills for all modelling tools.

Bronze Badge

The Bronze Badge represents an intermediate level of proficiency in energy and resource system modelling.

Intended Learning Objectives Upon achieving the Bronze Badge, holders should be able to:

- Understand and apply the principles of *basic national-scale CLEWs system modelling*
- Construct and run models using the chosen tool
- Identify and resolve common model debugging issues
- Analyse and interpret results from different modelling scenarios
- Explain how modelling results can inform policy decisions that involve trade-offs and synergies across sectors
- Demonstrate awareness of the limitations and assumptions *in basic CLEWs models*

Applicant needs to complete the following activities:

- Complete an intermediate-level in-person training course for CLEWs (e.g., EMP summer school or equivalent)
- Submit a project report or modelling case study demonstrating the application of learned skills

Required Evidence

- Upload certificate of training course completion
- Provide Zenodo links to materials produced from the course i.e. project report, posters, policy briefs etc.

Required Endorsement

- Contact a qualified badge holder (Silver or Associate Instructor) to review and endorse your application via Open Learn

Validity: 2 years, with re-application required if progression to Silver is not made

Silver Badge

The Silver Badge signifies advanced proficiency and the ability to apply modelling skills to real-world scenarios.

Intended Learning Objectives Upon achieving the Silver Badge, holders should be able to:

- Design and develop complex *CLEWs* models addressing specific real-world 'nexus' issues
- Implement advanced debugging techniques for more sophisticated models
- Critically evaluate scenario modelling results and their policy implications
- Communicate and document modelling outcomes effectively
- Adapt models to different geographical and socio-economic contexts

Applicant needs to have completed the following activities:

- Demonstrate 2 years of work/project experience *with CLEWs*, OR 1 year of work/project experience, plus a relevant publication

Required Evidence:

Submit ONE of the following:

- A completed Master's thesis *using a CLEWs framework*
- A published peer-reviewed paper (as 1st or 2nd author) *using CLEWs*
- A published report (or project output) *using CLEWs*

AND a letter of Reference

- from EITHER an academic or project supervisor (must highlight/confirm the required years experience)

Required Endorsement:

- Contact a qualified badge holder (Gold or Lead Instructor) to review and endorse your application via Open Learn

Validity: 4 years, with re-application required if progression to Gold is not made

Gold Badge

The Gold Badge represents mastery in energy and resource system modelling, including leadership and innovation in the field.

Intended Learning Objectives Upon achieving the Gold Badge, holders should be able to do all silver level requirements and demonstrate at least **two** of the following skills:

- Create innovative improvements and critical assessments of relevant modelling techniques and methodologies
- Manage and develop highly complex energy/resource models that are able to solve critical real-world problems
- Apply advanced coding and debugging skills to resolve intricate modelling challenges
- Translate complex modelling results into actionable policy recommendations for senior decision-makers

Applicant needs to complete the following activities:

- 5 years work/project experience with tool, OR PhD plus 2 years project experience

Required Evidence:

- Two letters of recommendation from existing Gold badge holders
- A CV extract demonstrating the required experience
- Provide links to 2 peer-reviewed academic publications or policy papers, as lead author, showcasing at least two of the above skills (skills can be demonstrated through alternative documentation i.e. a conference presentation, GitHub readme doc etc.)

Receiving the badge:

- Any current Gold badge holder will review and endorse your application via Open Learn

Validity - 10 years (before re-application required)

Instructor Badges

The Instructor Badge system recognizes the crucial role of trainers in capacity building for energy and resource system modelling. This two-tier system acknowledges the diverse skills required to effectively train others, and the different levels of engagement an instructor may have in a training (e.g. whether they are taking a leading or supporting role). Instructor Badges are tool specific and are valid in conjunction with an active proficiency badge in that tool (i.e. a

Lead instructor with a gold badge is able to 'instruct' at a higher level than a Lead instructor with a silver badge).

1. Associate Instructor Badge

The Associate Instructor Badge recognizes individuals who can effectively support and deliver specific components of training programs.

Intended Learning Objectives: Upon achieving the Associate Instructor Badge, holders should be able to -

- Design and deliver focused training modules on specific aspects of energy system modelling
- Adapt teaching methods to accommodate diverse learning styles and needs
- Provide constructive feedback to learners on their modelling exercises
- Effectively communicate complex modelling concepts to novice learners
- Support lead instructors in the overall delivery of training programs
- Demonstrate awareness of ethical considerations in energy system modelling instruction

Applicant needs to complete the following activities:

- Hold at least a Bronze proficiency badge in CLEWs
- Complete 40 hours of assisting/co-teaching with a Lead Instructor
- Lead one training session independently (with observation by a Lead Instructor)

Required Evidence:

- documentation of teaching hours, i.e. dates and timings of teaching events signed off by lead instructor
- a positive evaluation letter from a Lead Instructor, (that references participant self led teaching session)
- Provide Zenodo link to lesson plan used for independent training session

Required Endorsement:

- Contact a qualified Lead Instructor badge holder to review and endorse your application via Open Learn

Validity: Linked to the holder's proficiency badge validity

2. Lead Instructor Badge

The Lead Instructor Badge recognizes individuals capable of designing, organising, and leading comprehensive training programs in energy and resource system modelling. This badge aligns with the holder's proficiency level, determining course depth. For example, silver badge holders

teach fundamental concepts while gold badge holders deliver more advanced 'technical' content.

Intended Learning Objectives: Upon achieving the Lead Instructor Badge, holders should be able to -

- Design comprehensive, multi-level training programs in energy system modelling
- Develop advanced training materials and exercises that address real-world modelling challenges
- Evaluate and assess learners' modelling competencies across various skill levels
- Adapt training programs to suit diverse cultural and professional contexts
- Mentor Associate Instructors and support their professional development
- Integrate cutting-edge developments in energy modelling into training curricula
- Integrate ethical and cultural considerations into modelling instruction

Applicant needs to complete these activities:

- Hold at least a Silver proficiency badge in CLEWs
- Independently leading a full training program
- Create new training materials

Required Evidence:

Submit comprehensive teaching portfolio:

- Upload CV extract (or similar) outlining teaching experience
- Provide links to / or upload course materials showcasing an example of unique training/teaching materials (could include guideline steps, syllabuses, assessments etc.)
- Documentation of successful program delivery (EMP track or University Module or similar)- in the form of a class/course observation by a Gold or Lead badge holder [Template here](#)
- A letter of recommendation from a line manager, training program coordinator, head of department etc. that has oversight of your teaching/course and *is different* from the course/class assessor/observer.
- Submit a brief teaching philosophy (1-2 pages) that includes how you adapt training to different audiences and local contexts

Validity and Renewal:

To maintain the badge, instructors should engage in a minimum of 40 hours of training activities per year, and reapply for renewal every four years

- Renewal requires re-submission of a brief portfolio showcasing recent training activities (ideally with participant feedback).

Summary of Endorsement Levels

Badge level	Endorsement level (level required to endorse)
Bronze	Silver / Gold / Associate / Lead
Silver	Gold / Lead
Gold	2x Gold
Associate Instructor	Lead
Lead Instructor	Lead

Inaugural Badge Holders

To initiate the Energy and Resource System Modeling Proficiency Badge Scheme and acknowledge the existing expertise in the field, we have identified a select group of individuals whose extensive experience and contributions align with the criteria outlined for each badge level. These inaugural badge holders have been carefully selected based on their demonstrated proficiency, significant contributions to the field, and leadership in energy and resource system modelling.

In the interest of transparency and to maintain the integrity of the badge system, we provide below a brief overview of each inaugural badge holder's qualifications. This information demonstrates how their existing expertise and accomplishments meet or exceed the criteria established for their respective badge levels, even in the absence of the formal certification process that future badge earners will undergo.

It is important to note that these individuals serve as benchmarks for the level of expertise each badge represents. Their inclusion as inaugural badge holders not only recognises their achievements but also helps to establish a clear standard for future applicants.

Table of Inaugural Holders

	CLEWs		
	Silver	Gold	Lead
Leigh Martindale:	✓		✓
Kane Alexander	✓		✓
Kumbuso Joshua Nyoni:	✓		✓
Anastasios Karamaneas:	✓		
Alexandros Nikas:	✓		✓
Pacifique Koshikwinja Matabishi:	✓		✓
Camilla Lo Giudice:	✓		
Yalda Saedi	✓		
Nour Elislam Djedaa	✓		✓
Kavya Abeysundara:	✓		
Romain Akpahou	✓		
Nathan Johnson	✓		✓
Francesco Gardumi		✓	✓
Taco Niet		✓	✓
Jairo Quiros		✓	✓
Thomas Alfstad		✓	✓
Georgios Avgerinopoulos		✓	

List of inaugural badge holders:

—

GOLD + LEAD INSTRUCTOR

—

Francesco Gardumi

In regional training programs I led the OSeMOSYS and CLEWs part of week-long introductory workshops for several governments in Central and East Asia in collaboration with UNDESA. In 2020 I was part of a large CLEWs training program for 8 governments in Asia and the Pacific region that lasted several months, through which I co-created with colleagues at KTH, UNDESA and Simon Fraser University the material that fed into the first OpenLearn Create version of the Introduction to CLEWs course. I also guided the team from Iran in the creation of a regional CLEWs model to analyse scenarios of water scarcity. Later on I led the creation of a CLEWs model for Namibia in a long-term technical assistance program for the government, and I supervised students in the creation of CLEWs applications for Lao PDR and Zambia within CCG. I have co-supervised PhD students who had a key role in shaping the CLEWs-OSeMOSYS framework and am currently main supervisor of students working on advancing the CLEWs methodology. I defined the general scope of their research as fitting within the realms of addition of spatial and temporal granularity and assessment of uncertainties. Key publications (co-authored, supervised):

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1462901122002167>

<https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1748-9326/abd34f/meta>

I have been responsible and lecturer for an MSc course at KTH on Introduction to Energy Systems Analysis and Applications, which guides students in learning energy systems and CLEWs modelling using OSeMOSYS. I have designed and improved the course and the teaching material therein through time, among others aligning Intended Learning Outcomes with learning activities and assessment methods. I have been supporting trainer in several national and regional training programs of UNDESA and UNDP aimed at teaching government officials and academics CLEWs modelling with OSeMOSYS. I have led the CLEWs track of EMP-G (previously SDSummer School) in Trieste in 2021 and 2022, and supported the lead trainers afterwards. I am author of the original OpenLearn Create material for the Introduction to CLEWs course. Currently, I am organizing the CLEWs capacity development work of CCG in Zambia, and co-organising it in Lao PDR. Within these, I am also training a new PhD student whom I am main supervisor for to become supporting trainer (and later on main trainer) in CLEWs

workshops and capacity development programs. As part of the PhD supervision, I lead scientific work in the advancement of the CLEWs methodology.

Taco Niet

As a professor at Simon Fraser University in the School of Sustainable Energy Engineering I lead a research group developing OSeMOSYS and CLEWs models. I've been training at capacity development events with the UN and at EMP events since 2014 or so (not sure on the exact date) and have developed a graduate course on modelling at SFU. My research at Simon Fraser University includes publishing papers and leading Masters and Ph.D. students developing codes and workflows for both OSeMOSYS and CLEWs. I'll refer you to my Google Scholar profile for publications of relevance:

<https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=txWrYnAAAAAJ&hl=en>

Jairo Quiros

I developed CLEWs models (using OSeMOSYS) since 2019. I have developed CLEWs models for Costa Rica, Ecuador, Dominican Republic, Guatemala, Honduras, and Peru. In Costa Rica and Dominican Republic, I lead the development of regional CLEWs models with UNDESA. Currently, I am Professor at Loughborough University and the Deputy Director of CCG. I currently lead the development of the NDCs in Uganda, Costa Rica, Guatemala, Dominican Republic, Ecuador and these studies use a CLEWs model. I currently use CLEWs models to support Long Term Strategies in Ghana and Botswana.

Thomas Alfstad

Based on over two decades of experience in energy and environmental analysis, I meet all the criteria for the CLEWs – Gold Proficiency Badge. I have designed and led the development of complex, country-specific CLEWs models addressing real-world policy challenges, particularly in support of national climate strategies and NDCs. My modelling expertise spans multiple platforms, including MARKAL/TIMES, MESSAGE, OSeMOSYS, and LEAP, with proven ability to troubleshoot and refine sophisticated systems to ensure reliability and policy relevance. Throughout my roles at the United Nations, the International Atomic Energy Agency, and as an independent consultant, I have critically evaluated modelling results to inform policy decisions in over 20 countries. I have communicated these findings effectively through technical reports, training workshops, stakeholder consultations, and international conferences, ensuring clarity

for both technical and non-technical audiences. I have demonstrated strong capacity to adapt models to diverse geographical and socio-economic contexts—from multi-regional trade modelling in Southern Africa to integrated policy planning in Asia and Latin America. My track record in project design, capacity building, and stakeholder engagement further underscores my ability to align modelling tools with practical, country-specific needs. This experience directly reflects the advanced competencies required for the Gold Proficiency Badge.

GOLD

Georgios Avgerinopoulos

Based on nearly fifteen years of specialized experience in energy systems modelling and analysis, I meet all the criteria for the CLEWs – Gold Proficiency Badge. I have designed and implemented comprehensive energy models across multiple sectors, developing robust, adaptable tools for decision-making that address real-world policy and commercial challenges. My modelling expertise encompasses energy efficiency analysis for buildings and industry, stationary demand forecasting, and integrated energy system assessments, with demonstrated ability to coordinate complex modelling activities and deliver actionable insights. Throughout my roles at McKinsey & Company, Ricardo plc, Cornwall Insight, and as a freelance consultant, I have led energy modelling teams and applied rigorous economic frameworks to analytical problems across diverse contexts. I have effectively communicated technical findings to stakeholders through proposals, administrative coordination, and direct client engagement, ensuring clarity for both technical and business audiences. My experience spans varied geographical and sectoral applications—from leading the energy modelling team at Vivid Economics to coordinating energy efficiency initiatives at E3 Modelling, and contributing to quantitative and qualitative research agendas. This breadth of experience in model development, team leadership, and stakeholder engagement directly reflects the advanced competencies required for the Gold Proficiency Badge, demonstrating my ability to align sophisticated modelling tools with practical policy and commercial needs.

SILVER + LEAD INSTRUCTOR

Kane Alexander

Since graduating from my masters degree in 2022, entitled Climate Change, Politics and Policy, I have been heavily involved with CLEWs. I am Model Curator for CLEWs at CCG, this role entails being in charge of almost all things related to the CLEWs framework. I am the lead CLEWs trainer for CCG Energy Modelling Platforms and I have been involved with 7 events so far, across the world including India, Ghana, Brazil and Italy in 2024. I have helped teach masters courses for CLEWs at Loughborough University and I have supported masters students at both Loughborough University and Imperial College London. Whilst working with CLEWs I have developed my own materials, changed / updated the CLEWs Open University course, built country specific CLEWs models, led training across the world (even on my own), organise the Steering Committee meetings for CLEWs related professionals, have been a co-author for CLEWs-related papers and I am now writing a literature review of the CLEWs peer-reviewed literature.

Leigh Martindale

Through my work at Imperial College London on the EU's Diamond project, I have developed CLEWs models at both aggregated and disaggregated scales for Europe, demonstrating my ability to design and develop complex energy/resource system models for real-world applications; and making insights accessible to stakeholders. My role in capacity building initiatives across European and African institutions through the RE-INTEGRATE project has given me extensive experience in adapting models to different geographical and socio-economic contexts. Indeed, as a contributor to Climate Compatible Growth (CCG)- in particular, I have been an instructor at five of their Energy Modelling platform capacity building events , I create and design open-source modeling materials using CLEWs and OSeMOSYS. Experiences which have honed my skills in implementing advanced debugging techniques and communicating modeling outcomes effectively. My academic publication "Empowering Tomorrow's Problem Solvers: Nexus Thinking and CLEWs Modelling as a Pedagogical Approach to Wicked Problems" (2023) demonstrates my ability to critically reflect on teaching practices related to these modelling tools. Furthermore, as Masters Module Lead for 'Mapping and Modelling the Sustainable Development Goals' at Loughborough University, I have developed strong skills in teaching modelling as well as communicating and documenting modeling outcomes to students.

Pacifique Koshikwinja Matabishi

With more than 3 years of experience, I have acquired high proficiency in using CLEWs (Climate, Land, Energy, and Water systems) modeling framework, a comprehensive tool for analyzing the interconnections between key resource systems. Through my academic and research experience, I have developed strong expertise in constructing integrated models that investigate trade-offs and synergies across climate, land use, energy production, and water management. My experience includes developing bottom-up CLEWs models to evaluate the impacts of different policy initiatives, technological advancements, and resource management strategies on sustainability and development goals. My experience includes stakeholder engagement for the development of more inclusive models through a participatory modeling approach. I am also familiar with integrating CLEWs with tools like OSeMOSYS and LEAP for more detailed sectoral analysis. As part of an EU-funded project, I am currently leading the development of the Energy system model for the Democratic Republic of Congo and supporting many capacity-building projects as a trainer both at national and regional levels. Moreover, I have been a main contributor to the creation of a French version of the teaching material of the course available on the Open University platform.

Alexandros Nikas

Among several other models for energy planning and climate policy, I have been working with CLEWs since 2022. In particular, I have been coordinating the Horizon Europe IAM COMPACT project, in the context of which several model implementations of CLEWs are being developed and respective capacities built in Kenya, Sri Lanka, and Ethiopia; I have also been involved in efforts to disseminate these CLEWs model implementations in the community (e.g., by presenting the latter work, led by C. Boespflug, at the 2024 Integrated Assessment Modeling Consortium Meeting). In parallel, I have also been coordinating the Horizon Europe DIAMOND project, in the context of which two EU-wide implementations of the framework, CLEWs-EU, are being developed by Imperial College, the Cyprus Institute, and our team (at the Energy Policy Unit of the School of Electrical & Computer Engineering, at the National Technical University of Athens): the first, low-complexity implementation (<https://github.com/CLIMATE-DIAMOND/EU-CLEWS/tree/main/Aggregated%20EU%20Model>) features the EU as a single node (i.e., without regional disaggregation) to underpin stakeholder engagement in the project, while the second implementation is being developed to feature advanced regional disaggregation at the national level and to represent behavioural aspects, climate responses, and finance dynamics.

Since 2023, I have designed and introduced the comprehensive undergraduate course 'Decision support models for climate policy' within the School of Electrical & Computer Engineering curriculum at the National Technical University of Athens, which I teach alongside

my colleagues at the Energy Policy Unit. Its objective is to introduce students to state-of-the-art scientific paradigms and modelling tools for supporting energy planning and climate policy with a focus on mitigation (including economic, energy-system, and integrated assessment models), using different types of economic equilibrium, optimisation, and simulation modelling for the energy-economy-climate interactions. The didactic approach also emphasises the added value of other relevant frameworks, including for co-creation towards maximising participation and legitimacy, robustness of the scientific/modelling insights using a broad range of operational research approaches, sociotechnical analysis from a systems of innovation lens, climate governance mapping, etc. Among other modelling approaches/tools, the course includes two class lectures, plus one hands-on lab session with advanced training and exercises, on nexus modelling with CLEWs. Apart from the undergraduate course, I have co-designed the postgraduate 'Least-cost energy planning' course for PhD candidates at the School, including an associated CLEWs lecture. I am currently mentoring one PhD student on the development of an EU-focused implementation, CLEWs-EU.

Kumbuso Joshua Nyoni

With a robust background in energy and resource system modeling, I possess substantial practical experience with the CLEWs framework and advanced tools like OSeMOSYS. My expertise aligns with the CLEWs - Silver Proficiency Badge by demonstrating proficiency in designing, developing, and applying complex energy and resource models to address real-world challenges, such as enhancing policy coherence for sustainable development in Zambia.

Key achievements include:

Model Development and Scenario Analysis: Designed and implemented integrated models to assess Zambia's energy, water, and food systems under various climate change scenarios, such as Business-As-Usual, No Adaptation, and Climate-Adjusted Infrastructure. This work informed sustainable energy transitions, emphasizing low-carbon and resilient infrastructure solutions.

Policy Impact and Communication: Critically evaluated modeling results to derive actionable policy insights. Published findings on Zenodo and presented them at high-profile events, including the Hydro Symposium organized by the Kafue Gorge Regional Training Center. Additionally, presented research findings under the CLEWs Energy Modelling Community: Applications in Research, organized by CCG, demonstrating the ability to effectively document and communicate technical outcomes to diverse stakeholders.

Adaptation and Debugging: Successfully adapted modeling approaches for diverse socio-economic and geographic contexts. Utilized advanced debugging techniques to refine CLEWs-based models for robust policy analysis.

My work demonstrates a commitment to fostering knowledge sharing and capacity-building within the global energy modeling community through leadership in stakeholder engagement, interdisciplinary collaboration, and training initiatives.

My expertise and research experience position me as an ideal candidate for the CLEWs - Lead Instructor Badge. Through my published research, Enhancing Policy Coherence for Sustainable Development in Zambia: An Integrated Assessment Model (IAM)-Based Approach to the Climate-Water-Energy-Food Nexus, I have demonstrated advanced proficiency in applying the CLEWs framework to address critical resource challenges. This study, published on Zenodo, highlights my ability to develop sophisticated models, evaluate policy scenarios, and derive actionable insights to address complex, real-world challenges.

The research explores key scenarios such as Business-as-Usual (BAU), No Adaptation (NA), and Climate-Adjusted Infrastructure (CAI), showcasing a nuanced understanding of scenario planning and the policy implications of resource management strategies. By integrating diverse stakeholder inputs, I demonstrated an ability to adapt methodologies to various socio-economic and geographical contexts, a skill critical for designing impactful training programs.

Additionally, my work emphasizes clear and effective communication of technical outcomes, making complex modeling results accessible to policymakers and practitioners. This expertise in creating actionable policy recommendations and engaging stakeholders underscores my potential to mentor and guide aspiring professionals in CLEWs modeling, contributing to the advancement of modeling education and capacity-building globally.

Nour Elislam Djedaa

As a Researcher at the Applied Economics Research Centre for Development (CREAD), I have contributed to Algeria's National Energy Modelling Project (2019–2024), which established the foundation for integrated system modelling using open-source tools. Building on this, I have developed and co-led two new projects applying OSeMOSYS: the first, with the Energy Economics Team, assesses Algeria's Energy Transition and its macroeconomic impacts through integration with the E3M.dz model; the second, within the Natural Resources Economics and Environment Team and in collaboration with the Ministry of Agriculture, optimizes national strategies for durum-wheat self-sufficiency under water and land constraints. These experiences have strengthened my ability to design and debug complex CLEWs-based models, evaluate multi-sector scenarios, and interpret results within policy frameworks. I routinely ensure internal consistency and reproducibility, linking technical findings to socio-economic implications. In parallel, as a member of the PRIMA-funded MORFeuS (WEFE) project, I contribute to regional efforts promoting integrated resource governance and cross-sectoral resilience. Together, these activities demonstrate a solid capacity to adapt CLEWs methodologies to diverse contexts and to communicate modelling outcomes that inform sustainable, evidence-based policy.

Nathan Johnson

Below, I evidence Silver proficiency in CLEWs. Over the past year I have worked on DIAMOND updating and fully "opening" multiple complex European CLEWs models, improving spatio-temporal granularity and data pipelines. This experience follows a two years of hands-on experience in CLEWs projects across CCG. I have also supervised several MSc students working on CLEWs projects. Together this far exceeds two years of continuous CLEWs-related work. More broadly, I design and develop a wide range of complex, policy-relevant models (e.g., integrating techno-economics and hourly demand), implement advanced debugging for sophisticated codebases (unit tests, profiling, reproducible ETL and validation at scale), and critically evaluate scenario outputs to derive clear policy insights for governments and utilities. I communicate and document outcomes through peer-reviewed publications and widely read policy/industry reports, and by delivering capacity-building workshops for African and EU stakeholders. My modelling is adapted across geographies and socio-economic contexts—from EU CLEWs updates to planning and training in across Africa—demonstrating portability and stakeholder relevance. Where helpful, I draw on adjacent work (Demand Ninja/Renewables Ninja; Electric Insights) to support transparent, reproducible CLEWs applications.

SILVER

—

Kavya Abeyesundara

I am working as a sustainability consultant for Climate Compatible Growth and have helped develop CLEWs models that have gone on to inform the Nationally Determined Contributions of Türkiye and Uganda. The CLEWs model developed for Türkiye spanned across 7-sectors: power, transport, industry, buildings, land, agriculture and waste and was the first CLEWs++ model to be developed at CCG. The Uganda model was a detailed foundational model focusing on energy, land, and water systems. I have also led workshops on CLEWs in Türkiye, the 2025 EMP-G, and at Imperial College, developing capability in CLEWs across local teams and students.

Anastasios Karamaneas

I have been working with CLEWs for around 2 years on the premises of the Horizon Europe DIAMOND project in which we are developing a CLEWs model for the EU. We have already developed an aggregated version for the EU and we are now working on a disaggregated version. Moreover, I have participated in and been certified on the ICTP Summer School 2023 on the CLEWs courses track. Lastly, I have working and research experience with OSeMOSYS and OSeMBE, with which I have also made a couple of publications (OSeMOSYS in a scientific paper and OSeMBE in a scientific conference).

Camilla Lo Giudice

I am a PhD candidate at KTH and I am currently focused on advancing the CLEWs methodology. Over this period, I have been actively involved in two major projects that integrate CLEWs modelling into global and regional decision-making processes. As part of the IAMcompact project, I coordinate and supervise CLEWs modelling activities in Kenya and Sri Lanka (Gardumi et al., 2024). Additionally, I am developing a multi-regional CLEWs model for the case study of Ethiopia. The research will focus on increasing the temporal and spatial resolution, allowing the representation of crop cycling and understanding the impact of erratic precipitation patterns on the use of resource. Moreover, I am contributing to the development of a workflow which standardizes CLEWs outputs into IAMc format while also quantifying the modelling results through the use of indicators. A second project I am involved in is Climate Compatible Growth (CCG) . My work includes capacity-building activities in Zambia and EMPs, while advancing modelling approaches for smart resource use and adaptation strategies. Through these projects, I have gained extensive experience in designing complex resource system models, debugging sophisticated workflows, critically assessing scenario results, and effectively communicating modelling outcomes to diverse stakeholders.

Yalda Saedi

I am applying for this badge based on my strong background in CLEWs modelling, supported by my EMP training, MSc thesis, and development of the GeoCLEWs. My work extends open-source CLEWs modelling for Kenya, focusing on high-resolution land and water data. As part of this, I developed GeoCLEWs, an open-source Python-based tool that enables detailed land and water system representation using GAEZ v4 and FAOSTAT datasets. GeoCLEWs, shared on GitHub, facilitates CLEWs model development in a clewsy-compatible format, providing automated data collection, preparation, and analysis. My MSc thesis, titled "Enhancing Open-Source CLEWs Models with High-Resolution Land and Water Data", was supervised by Dr. Taco Niet and built on two years of experience in CLEWs modelling. Additionally, I developed Laos Cascade Hydropower Plants in OSeMOSYS and contributed to

capacity-building efforts. During my internship at CATALYSTE+, I contributed to the organization and facilitation of a four-day technical and policy workshop in Kenya, supporting local expertise in CLEWs modelling. I have also been actively involved as a trainer in Energy Modelling Platforms (EMP) over the past years, supporting knowledge-sharing in sustainable energy system modelling.

Dr. Romain Akpahou

Dr. Romain Akpahou has over five years of experience in teaching, consulting, and renewable energy project development. His expertise includes energy systems modelling, climate resilience, policy analysis, and transport decarbonization in developing countries. He has led and contributed to projects focused on rural electrification, clean cooking, and sustainable energy planning. He has advanced skills in Climate, Land, Energy, and Water systems (CLEWs) modelling framework, particularly in supporting national planning and decision-making. He currently serves as a research consultant with the Climate Compatible Growth (CCG) program, where he develops and calibrates CLEWs models for selected countries under the Data-to-Deal (D2D) framework. His responsibilities include leading data collection, processing, integration, and validation to support robust, evidence-based policy analysis. He collaborates closely with national stakeholders, the lead expert consultant, and the D2D lead to ensure model outputs are policy-relevant and actionable. He has authored multiple peer-reviewed publications and contributed to the development of knowledge tools to support decision-makers. His work is dedicated to advancing climate resilience and sustainable energy transitions in developing contexts, helping countries mitigate climate change while achieving their development goals.